

Please cite this report as:

Nangle, B., Lamberty, L., Krivobokova, T., Azadi, T. & d’Haenens, L. (2026). *Theoretical Report on the Differences between Traditional and Online Extreme Discourse and How these Differences Shape the Acceptance and Dissemination of Online Extreme Discourse*. KU Leuven, Leuven: DEMINE.

Disclaimer

DEMINE is supported by the European Union’s Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Networks (MSCA-DN), under Grant Agreement no 101167978.

Theoretical Report on the Differences between Traditional and Online Extreme Discourse and How these Differences Shape the Acceptance and Dissemination of Online Extreme Discourse

Work package 3 – Deliverable 3.1

Submission date: April 30, 2026

Lead beneficiary: University of Padova

Authors: Benjamin Nangle, Lea-Marie Lamberty, Tatiana Krivobokova, Tania Azadi, & Leen d'Haenens

Table of Contents

- 1. Executive Summary..... 4
- 2. About DEMINE 6
- 3. Introduction 8
- 4. Methodology..... 9
- 5. Results 10
 - 5.1 Insights from the Scoping Review 10
 - 5.2 Anti-migrant Discourse in Traditional Media..... 12
 - 5.2.1 Role, Content, and Structural Characteristics of Traditional Media 12
 - 5.2.2 Dominant Discourses and Mechanism Representation in Traditional Media of Migration 13
 - 5.2.3 Anti-Migration Discourse in German Traditional Media..... 14
 - 5.2.4 Effects of Anti-Migration Discourse on Migrants and Society 16
 - 5.2.5 Broader implications 16
 - 5.3 Focus on Digital Platforms as Sites of Far-Right Acculturation..... 17
 - 5.3.1 Memetic Communication and Multimodal Mainstreaming 18
 - 5.3.2 Affective Strategies and the Role of Positive Emotion 18
 - 5.3.3 Algorithmic Architecture and the Ecology of Amplification 20
 - 5.3.4 Inauthentic Localisation, Sockpuppetry, and Serial Misattribution..... 21
 - 5.3.5 Comment Sections as Acculturative Infrastructure 22
- 6. Conclusion and Recommendations..... 23
 - 6.1 Conclusion..... 23
 - 6.2 Recommendations 23
- 7. References 25

1. Executive Summary

This report examines the structural and communicative differences between traditional and online extreme discourse, with particular attention to how these differences shape the acceptance, dissemination, and normalisation of such content. It combines a scoping review of 582 peer-reviewed articles with original empirical analysis of far-right social media content, drawing on two multimodal content analyses of Instagram conducted within the DEMINE project.

The scoping review confirms that traditional and online extreme discourse share core discursive repertoires, dehumanisation, othering, threat construction, and moralised language, but that the infrastructural conditions governing their production, circulation, and reception differ fundamentally. Traditional media are characterised by institutional gatekeeping, elite sourcing, and predominantly text-based communication. These features constrain, though do not eliminate, the reach and intensity of extreme content. Online environments, by contrast, are defined by decentralised production, multimodal communication, algorithmic amplification, and the near-total absence of editorial accountability.

Analysis of anti-migration discourse in German traditional media illustrates this spectrum from implicit structural bias to overt ideological extremism: mainstream outlets such as Tagesschau reproduce implicit, structurally embedded biases through elite-driven framing and crisis orientation, while explicitly far-right outlets such as *Compact* deploy overtly exclusionary, emotionalised rhetoric. Both, however, contribute to the representation of migrants as a homogeneous threat rather than as individuals with agency.

In online environments, extreme discourse is further distinguished by several dynamics with no clear equivalent in traditional media. Most recognisable in the online context of social media, memetic communication enables ideological content to travel multimodally through entertainment channels, lowering thresholds for engagement and resistance. Affective strategies, including humour, nostalgia, and aspirational aesthetics, extend the emotional repertoire of far-right messaging beyond fear and outrage, facilitating mainstreaming among audiences who would not engage with overtly political material. Algorithmic recommendation systems create recursive amplification loops that systematically surface and intensify extreme content, producing what the report terms an affective–discursive ecology in which extremist narratives become ambiently familiar rather than overtly confrontational.

The report also identifies practices specific to online environments: sockpuppetry and inauthentic localisation fabricate the appearance of domestic grassroots sentiment; serial misattribution recycles decontextualised footage to manufacture transnational grievance resonance; and participatory comment cultures function as acculturative spaces in which ideological content is clarified and escalated beneath the threshold of automated moderation, through emoji-coded dog whistles and coordinated dogpiling.

A consistent gap across the literature concerns the role of platforms themselves as infrastructural actors. Algorithmic design, monetisation incentives, and content moderation architectures shape the visibility and circulation of extreme discourse in ways that remain undertheorised relative to the attention given to users and political actors.

The report concludes that online environments do not simply scale up pre-existing forms of extreme discourse but qualitatively transform its mode of articulation, its affective register, and its trajectory of normalisation. Effective responses will require analytical frameworks and policy interventions attentive to these platform-specific dynamics, rather than extensions of approaches developed for traditional media contexts.

2. About DEMINE

DEMINE goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.

- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarisation and radicalisation to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarized world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

This theoretical report examines the differences between traditional (offline) and online forms of extreme discourse, with particular attention to how these differences shape the acceptance, circulation, and normalisation of such narratives. It starts from the premise that digital environments do not merely extend pre-existing forms of communication but fundamentally reconfigure the conditions under which extreme discourse is produced, encountered, and engaged with.

The report identifies key structural and interactional features of online platforms, such as scalability, persistence, anonymity, and algorithmic curation, that enable the rapid and far-reaching dissemination of extreme content. These affordances are contrasted with the constraints of traditional communication channels, including face-to-face interaction and legacy media, where gatekeeping, social accountability, and contextual cues tend to moderate expression and limit diffusion.

In addition, the report analyses how specific dynamics of online interaction, such as echo chambers, networked publics, and algorithmic amplification, shape patterns of exposure and engagement. These dynamics can intensify reinforcement processes, lower thresholds for participation, and contribute to the perceived legitimacy and normalisation of extreme discourse.

By comparing offline and online communicative environments, the report aims to clarify the mechanisms through which digital infrastructures transform the propagation and reception of extreme views. In doing so, it provides a conceptual foundation for understanding how contemporary media ecosystems facilitate the diffusion and acceptance of extreme discourse across different audiences and contexts. This report adopts a twofold approach that combines a structured review of existing scholarship with an original empirical analysis. The aim is to both synthesise current knowledge on extreme discourse across traditional and online media, and to extend this knowledge through a focused, multimodal study of social media content.

Throughout this report, the terms "traditional media" and "online media" are used to denote analytically distinct communicative environments, differentiated primarily by their infrastructural logics rather than their content. Traditional media refers to institutionally produced and editorially mediated communication distributed through print, broadcast television, and radio. These channels are characterised by centralised production, professional gatekeeping, linear distribution, and relatively stable accountability structures. Online media, by contrast, refers to digitally networked platforms (including social media, short-form video platforms, and participatory web environments) defined by decentralised production, algorithmic curation, scalable distribution, and the near-absence of editorial oversight. The report acknowledges that these categories are not hermetically sealed: legacy outlets maintain online presences, and platform-distributed content increasingly shapes traditional news agendas. The analytic distinction is nonetheless maintained because the infrastructural differences between the two environments (in particular the replacement of gatekeeping with engagement-maximising recommendation systems) produce qualitatively different conditions for the production, circulation, and normalisation of extreme discourse. It is these infrastructural conditions, rather than the ideological content of any given outlet, that the report's comparative framework is designed to illuminate.

A further terminological clarification concerns the concept of extreme discourse itself. The report uses this term to refer to communicative practices that construct sharp in-group/out-group boundaries,

dehumanise or threaten targeted groups, and normalise or legitimate exclusionary political positions, in this context, with particular reference to migration. This definition is deliberately broad. As the scoping review confirms, the field lacks a standardised definition, and what counts as extreme is contextually constructed rather than fixed: content that would be considered fringe in one media environment may circulate as mainstream in another. The report therefore treats extremity as a scalar and relational property rather than a binary category, operating along a spectrum from the structurally embedded implicit bias of mainstream journalism to the overtly exclusionary and dehumanising rhetoric of far-right media. This spectrum framing is not intended to flatten meaningful differences between, for instance, crisis-driven migration coverage in a public broadcaster and the eliminationist language of a far-right magazine. Rather, it reflects the report's core argument that extreme discourse is not confined to self-identified extremist actors but is reproduced, in varying registers and with varying intensity, across the broader media landscape.

4. Methodology

First, a scoping review was conducted to map the breadth and diversity of existing research on extreme discourse in both traditional and online media. Following established scoping review protocols, this component systematically identifies, selects, and synthesises relevant academic literature across disciplines. The objective is not to provide an exhaustive or evaluative meta-analysis, but rather to clarify key concepts, identify dominant theoretical frameworks, and highlight areas of convergence and divergence in the literature. This approach is particularly suited to an emerging and interdisciplinary field characterised by conceptual fragmentation. The DEMINE scoping review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework to ensure a transparent and reproducible identification and screening process. A comprehensive literature search was conducted across three major bibliographic databases: EBSCO (n = 423), Scopus (n = 1020), and Web of Science (n = 6803). This search strategy resulted in a total of 8246 records identified for potential inclusion. Following aggregation of the retrieved references, duplicate entries were systematically removed (n = 1097), yielding a deduplicated dataset of 7149 unique records that proceeded to the subsequent screening stages. Following title- and abstract-level screening and full-text eligibility assessment, 582 full-text articles were retained and included in the DEMINE scoping review, constituting the final evidence base of the study. Of these, 255 articles specifically focused on content, alongside studies addressing audience characteristics and interventions. The analysis of this subsample was of most direct relevance to the current report.

Second, the report includes a focused qualitative case study of traditional media discourse in Germany. This component is based on a comparative analysis of selected media outlets representing different positions within the German media landscape, namely Tagesschau and Compact. The selection follows a most-different case logic, allowing for the examination of how anti-migration discourse operates across both mainstream and explicitly ideological media contexts within the same national setting.

Third, the report incorporates an amalgamation of two original multimodal studies of social media content (Nangle & d'Haenens, 2026; Nangle & d'Haenens, under review), which serves to ground and extend the insights derived from the literature. This empirical component focuses on the analysis of selected social media materials, taking into account the interplay of textual, visual, and interactional elements. By adopting a multimodal perspective, the study captures how extreme discourse is not only articulated through language but also through images, symbols, memes, and platform-specific communicative practices. The analysis pays particular attention to how meaning is constructed across

modes, how engagement is shaped through platform affordances, and how discursive strategies contribute to the visibility and uptake of extreme content. In doing so, it complements the scoping review by providing fine-grained insights into the communicative dynamics that underpin the dissemination and acceptance of extreme discourse in digital environments.

Fourth, the report draws on a complementary DEMINE study examining 40 German-language YouTube vodcasts published between December 2024 and August 2025, comprising over 50 hours of content from AfD politicians, Identitarian activists, and alternative media figures (Arena & Opgenhaffen, 2026, referred to in Arena, Nangle, Azadi & d'Haenens, 2026). The analysis identifies three integrated mechanisms through which extreme content circulates in long-form video without triggering moderation thresholds: institutional delegitimisation, which systematically portrays media, academia, courts, and civil society as captured by hostile elite interests; statistical weaponisation, which deploys selective demographic data, crime statistics, and pseudo-scientific projections to normalise extreme narratives as empirical common sense; and deniability engineering, which substitutes euphemistic language, cultural framing, and centrist self-positioning for explicitly prosecutable expression, rendering individual statements formally defensible while their cumulative effect reconstructs extremist logic. Crucially, 90 percent of the sampled videos include explicit meta-commentary on these strategies, speakers discuss Overton window shifts, coach peers on effective formulations, and track progress in what can now be said publicly — confirming that mainstreaming operates as a deliberate and transmissible technique rather than incidental rhetorical drift. The study further highlights content format as an independent variable: the extended runtime of long-form video provides the conversational space for all three mechanisms to unfold within a single piece of content, a condition the short-form environment structurally forecloses.

Together, these components enable a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon, linking broad theoretical patterns to concrete communicative practices.

5. Results

The scoping review provides a systematic mapping of how extreme discourse has been conceptualised, defined, and empirically studied across traditional and online media, with the aim of identifying key patterns, gaps, and shifts in the field.

5.1 Insights from the Scoping Review

The **scoping review** shows that extreme discourse across both traditional and online media is built from largely overlapping discursive repertoires, such as dehumanisation, othering, threat construction, and moralised language, but that the conditions under which these repertoires are produced, circulated, and interpreted differ fundamentally between the two environments.

At the level of **discursive form**, traditional media are predominantly characterised by structured, text-based and institutionally mediated communication (e.g., news articles, political speeches), whereas online environments exhibit a broader range of **multimodal and hybrid forms**, including memes, images and interactive formats. While the literature remains heavily text-centred, the review indicates that online discourse increasingly relies on the **interplay between textual, visual, and interactional elements**, which intensifies affective resonance and facilitates reinterpretation and recirculation of extreme content.

Moreover, differences emerge in terms of **actors and production dynamics**. Traditional media environments are dominated by institutional actors, such as journalists, editors, and political elites, whose communicative practices are shaped by professional norms and gatekeeping structures. In contrast, online environments are marked by a strong presence of **ordinary users and networked publics**, alongside political and fringe actors. The dataset shows a clear emphasis on user-generated content in social media, where discourse is produced in a decentralised and participatory manner, enabling a much wider range of actors to contribute to the circulation of extreme narratives.

The review also highlights differences in **levels of analysis and circulation dynamics**. Traditional media studies often operate at meso- and macro-levels, focusing on framing patterns, agenda-setting, and institutional discourse. Online media research, by contrast, frequently combines micro-level analysis of individual posts or comments with meso-level attention to **networked circulation**, such as how narratives spread across platforms and communities. This reflects the structural shift from relatively linear communication flows to **highly networked and recursive dissemination processes**.

Most crucially for the DEMINE objectives, the review points to differences in **mechanisms of acceptance and normalisation**. While traditional media may contribute to the legitimisation of certain discourses through framing and repetition, online environments introduce additional dynamics that intensify these processes. The literature consistently links online discourse to **affective amplification (fear, threat, moral emotions), reinforcement within like-minded communities, and reduced social accountability**. These dynamics are closely aligned with the prominence of affective and discourse-oriented conceptual lenses identified in the review, suggesting that **emotional resonance and boundary-making processes are central to the uptake of extreme discourse**.

The absence of standardised definitions across the literature, combined with reliance on **implicit and operational coding schemes**, indicates that extreme discourse is not a fixed category but is **contextually constructed within specific communicative environments**. This flexibility appears more pronounced in online contexts, where rapidly evolving formats and vernaculars (e.g., memes, coded language) require adaptive analytical approaches. For the purposes of this review, extreme discourse was operationalised broadly to encompass communicative practices that construct sharp in-group/out-group boundaries, dehumanise or threaten targeted groups, and normalise or legitimate exclusionary political positions, with particular reference to migration-related content. This deliberately inclusive definition reflects the field's own conceptual fragmentation: as the review confirms, no standardised definition has achieved cross-disciplinary consensus, and the most consequential forms of extreme content are frequently those that resist explicit categorisation.

Finally, the review suggests that online environments do not simply increase the *amount* of extreme discourse but alter its **mode of articulation and trajectory of dissemination**. The combination of multimodality, participatory production, and networked circulation enables extreme discourse to become more **diffuse, iterative, and socially embedded**, thereby lowering thresholds for engagement and contributing to gradual processes of normalisation.

The term "online environments" is used here to refer to digitally networked platforms characterised by algorithmic curation, decentralised production, and participatory audience engagement. The report acknowledges that the boundary between traditional and online media is increasingly porous: mainstream media organisations maintain active social media presences, and institutional actors routinely disseminate content through platform-native channels. The analytic distinction

nonetheless holds at the level of infrastructure, what differs is not who produces content but the algorithmic, economic, and participatory conditions under which it circulates and is received.

In sum, the scoping review indicates that the key differences lie not in the core discursive building blocks of extremity, but in the **media-specific infrastructures that shape how these elements are assembled, circulated, and received**. Traditional media tend to constrain and contextualise extreme discourse through institutional mediation, whereas online environments enable its **acceleration, amplification, and affective embedding**, thereby reshaping both its acceptance and its societal impact.

A gap in the literature concerns the role of platforms themselves. While research focuses extensively on users, political actors, and media organisations, digital platforms as infrastructural actors remain under-theorised. Yet processes such as algorithmic amplification, content moderation, and monetisation shape the visibility and circulation of extreme discourse in ways that have no clear parallel in traditional media environments.

Together, these observations suggest that the field possesses a rich but unevenly adapted toolkit for studying extreme discourse in digital contexts. The analytical categories largely developed in offline or early digital research retain substantial value but require extension rather than replacement to account for the distinctive affordances, actor configurations, and infrastructural conditions of contemporary online communication.

The scoping review was conducted in collaboration with the wider DEMINE consortium. The authors gratefully acknowledge the contributions of doctoral candidates and supervisors across the network whose collective efforts produced the evidence base on which this report draws.

5.2 Anti-migrant Discourse in Traditional Media

5.2.1 Role, Content, and Structural Characteristics of Traditional Media

Amongst growing digitalisation of media and news, traditional media such as newspapers and television remain a central arena for opinion-making and shaping. This type of media is characterised by high levels of institutionalisation and professionalisation. Nevertheless, the narratives and perspectives covered are primarily decided by editorial processes and priorities as well as the political and economic interests of large media conglomerates and wealthy individuals, who own the vast majority of traditional media (Agarwal et al., 2023). Information is largely sourced from political and educated elites, for instance, government actors, institutions, and experts, leaving little space for the voices of marginalised groups such as migrants (Pearson et al., 2025). Thus, traditional media serve as a discursive filter shaping how migration is interpreted, problematised, and politicised.

Traditional media has long been theorised as a central intermediary in democratic systems, structuring public discourse through routines of selection, verification, and prioritisation. Classic accounts of gatekeeping (White, 1950; Shoemaker & Vos, 2009) and agenda-setting (McCombs & Shaw, 1972) remain foundational for understanding how news organisations influence not only what issues are visible, but also how they are framed. More recent scholarship revisits these mechanisms under contemporary conditions of hybrid media systems. In these systems, legacy outlets continue to hold agenda-setting power, although in recent decades digital actors provide significant competition (Chadwick, 2017). Empirical studies confirm that traditional media still shape interpretive frames. In migration coverage, this pattern shows up repeatedly (Maurer, 2024). This reinforces the observation

that editorial processes function as a discursive filter, structure the boundaries of legitimate debate, and amplify certain, often biased, perspectives over others.

The content of traditional media relies heavily on elite sources and institutional narratives, and it becomes easier to see once one looks at who actually gets quoted. This contributes to the reproduction of dominant viewpoints. Research on sourcing practices demonstrates a systematic preference for official actors, including government representatives and established experts, due to norms of credibility and efficiency (Bennett, 1990; Hertzum, 2022). This “indexing” dynamic limits the range of perspectives represented in news coverage, particularly in contentious policy areas. Recent studies confirm that migration coverage in mainstream media tends to privilege political elites and frame migrants through lenses of security, crisis, or economic burden (Eberl et al., 2018; Krzyżanowski et al., 2018). Such patterns align with the earlier argument that marginalised voices remain underrepresented, as structural newsroom practices and professional norms systematically constrain whose perspectives are deemed newsworthy.

There is also a more structural side to this. Traditional media organisations are part of concentrated ownership systems and face economic pressures that influence both content and editorial choices. Research on media ownership shows increasing consolidation and the impact of corporate and political interests on news production (Martin & McCrain, 2019). These structural factors interact with professional norms, creating what is called a “hierarchy of influences” on media output (Shoemaker & Reese, 2014). In migration coverage, this often results in narratives that reflect broader political agendas and market interests, favoring conflict-driven stories that attract viewers while aligning with dominant ideological views (Berry et al., 2016; Fuller, 2024). Together, these structural features strengthen the role of traditional media as an institutional filter, as mentioned earlier, shaping not only how migration is seen but also how it becomes politicised and understood publicly.

5.2.2 Dominant Discourses and Mechanism Representation in Traditional Media of Migration

Media does not merely report neutrally on reality, but by selecting, framing, and repeating narratives, it actively moulds social reality. By this means, it can contribute to the construction of a migration “reality” through normalising certain interpretations, for instance, migration as a problem or as an opportunity.

One of the most dominant narratives frames migration as a threat to public order and security by portraying migrants as violent or criminal. Such framing undermines evidence-based reasoning and differentiated perspectives on migrants’ lived experiences. It also furthers hostile beliefs about migration, justifying exclusionary policies such as stricter migration laws or militarised border control. However, the framing of migration as a threat is not limited to security concerns but spills over into other areas of life. A common narrative is migration being an economic threat, for instance, by presenting migrants as taking advantage of socialist policies or as a cultural threat to national identity and unity (Nangle & Blažyte, 2026).

The framing of migration as a threat goes hand in hand with the criminalisation and illegalisation of migrants, which increases the legitimisation of exceptional government action such as pushbacks, extended detention, and police violence. In this narrative, migration is associated with crime, terrorism, and deviant sexuality, reinforcing not only the interpretation of migration as a security threat but also as a gendered and cultural threat to local women and gender norms (Nangle & Blažyte, 2026).

Irrespective of factual reality, migration is frequently described as a “crisis” by concentrating on single exceptional events. By enlarging the perceived magnitude and creating a sense of urgency, this style of framing constructs feelings of anxiety and panic among media consumers. Thus, it increases public approval of restrictive measures and rash policy decisions (Nangle & Blažyte, 2026).

Such narratives are often perpetuated indirectly through language. Terminology such as “illegal migrants” portrays migration as inherently unlawful, blurring the lines between criminal activity and administrative status violation. Moreover, labels including “illegal migrant”, “asylum seeker”, and “refugee” increase the dehumanisation of individuals as homogeneous groups fitting into rigid categories of those “deserving” and those “undeserving” of relocation. Abstract representations of migration, for instance, “wave” or “surge”, further decrease migrants’ individuality and humanity, lowering empathy towards them (Nangle & Blažyte, 2026). Therefore, labels can impose a moral evaluation and hold ideological significance. As such, they help legitimise policies, form public opinion, and construct emotionality or disengagement.

Discourse, particularly in traditional media, is not only shaped by what is said but also by which details and perspectives are omitted. A lack of analysis of structural migration causes centres narratives from the host country only and portrays migration not as an often life-saving need imposed by outside forces such as political stakeholders or a legacy of exploitation. Instead, it implies that migration is a solely personal choice, thus reinforcing the narrative of migrants deciding to leave their home country to take advantage of socialist policies elsewhere (Nangle & Blažyte, 2026). Furthermore, limited coverage of migrants’ lived experiences and positive interactions between migrants and locals underrepresents human perspectives in migration and oversimplifies migration as a largely political and purely challenging matter (Maurer et al, 2021). The omission of specific narratives is primarily influenced by concentrated media ownership, political coercion, and journalists’ self-censorship, for instance, when covering influential actors and institutions (Nangle & Blažyte, 2026).

5.2.3 Anti-Migration Discourse in German Traditional Media

Germany provides a particularly relevant case for examining anti-migration discourse, as migration has become a highly politicised and socially contested issue, particularly since the 2015 refugee inflow, which marked a turning point in public and media debates (Krzyżanowski et al., 2018; Eberl et al., 2018). Research shows that migration functions as a central political cleavage in Germany, shaping both public attitudes and electoral dynamics, while the rise of the populist radical-right party *Alternative für Deutschland (AfD)* has further intensified the salience of exclusionary and threat-based narratives (Arzheimer, 2015; Hutter & Kriesi, 2019). Within this context, focusing on German traditional media allows for an analysis of how such discourses are constructed within a single, highly relevant national setting. The selection of *Tagesschau* and *Compact* is particularly instructive, as they represent contrasting positions within the media landscape: a mainstream public broadcaster shaped by professional norms, public accountability, and elite sourcing, and an explicitly ideological outlet aligned with far-right actors. Analysing these two cases enables a comparative examination of how anti-migration discourse operates both through implicit, structurally embedded framing and overt, exclusionary rhetoric, thereby illustrating the broader spectrum of extreme discourse within traditional media (Maurer et al., 2021; Krzyżanowski et al., 2018).

5.2.3.1 Structural and Implicit Bias in *Tagesschau*

Tagesschau is the main news outlet of the public broadcaster ARD. It is the most watched news programme across all ages and is widely perceived as trustworthy and objective (ndr.de, 2024). While

it serves as a benchmark for mainstream German journalism, it nevertheless reproduces implicit, structural biases.

Migration coverage in *Tagesschau* is heavily guided by current events. It primarily features political actors, institutions, and their decisions (Maurer et al, 2021). Migrants' own perspectives are rarely included, limiting their representation as individuals with active agency. Thus, migration discourse in *Tagesschau* is elite-driven and framed as a political issue, not a social and human reality. Additionally, migration-related coverage peaks during major events and crises, portraying it as an exceptional but ongoing matter characterised by instability and urgency (Maurer et al, 2021). By primarily presenting migrants and refugees in crisis scenarios, not individual contexts, they are portrayed as one homogeneous group in need of help.

75% of coverage on migration causes in *Tagesschau* were security-related, for instance, escaping war or persecution. Although this frames migration as a human need for survival, migrants were portrayed in a highly negative light. In comparison with five other news outlets across the political spectrum, *Tagesschau* places second in representing migrants most negatively, just barely behind the tabloid *BILD*. In four out of the six outlets analyzed, including *Tagesschau*, immigration is primarily displayed as a danger rather than an opportunity. However, *Tagesschau* described migrants' behavior toward locals as almost exclusively negative, overtaking all other outlets. Locals' behavior towards migrants also received more negative than positive coverage in *Tagesschau* but was portrayed much more favorably than migrants' behavior (Maurer et al, 2021). This framing creates the impression of a confrontational relationship between locals and migrants, mostly provoked by the latter.

Overall, *Tagesschau's* coverage of migration is ambivalent. On the one hand, migrants are depicted as victims in need of help, on the other hand, as a risk to public order. Their anti-migration discourse operates through elite sourcing, subtle framing, and crisis orientation. Thus, the negative framing of migration in *Tagesschau* is not overt but structural and implicit.

5.2.3.2 Explicit and Ideological Framing in *Compact*

The far-right print magazine *Compact* was established by the activist Jürgen Elsässer to provide a platform for far-right extremists and has an anti-establishment agenda. It aims at shifting political discourse to the right by mixing conspiracy theories, misinformation, and threat scenarios with facts. They work closely with the right-wing party AfD ("Alternative for Germany") and the anti-Islam far-right extremist movement PEGIDA ("Patriotic Europeans Against the Islamisation of the West"). According to *Compact*, their monthly circulation consists of 40,000 copies on average (Verfassungsschutz Brandenburg, 2022).

Compact's migration discourse represents an extreme pole. Their anti-migration messages are explicit and frequently utilise alarmist language:

A war is being waged against the Germans [...]. This war is being waged from within – by politicians – and from without – by gang rapists, knife-wielding attackers, assailants, and murderers from foreign cultures. Germans are being hunted down, raped, beaten, stabbed,

driven out, and murdered – in their own country (Verfassungsschutz Brandenburg, 2022, p. 56).¹

Compact frames migration as a violent threat to national security by employing an “us versus them” narrative. Migrants are portrayed as cultural “others” and a danger to Germans, who are depicted as helpless victims. This narrative is amplified through emotionalised and alarmist language such as “war”, “knife-wielding”, and “hunted down”, which appeals to readers’ fear through exaggeration. The reproduction of conspiracy theories like locals being violated and replaced by migrants further supports that narrative. Thus, *Compact*’s use of explicitly exclusionary language and conspiracy theories increases the dehumanisation of migrants and hostility towards them.

5.2.3.3 Comparison between *Tagesschau* and *Compact*

While *Tagesschau*’s covert and institutionalised bias is created through subtle and elite-driven framing, *Compact* employs explicitly exclusionary narratives as well as emotionalised and alarmist language to disseminate its explicit anti-migrant ideology. Nevertheless, both contribute to the representation of migrants as a problem, threat, and homogenous group without agency. Therefore, anti-migration discourse exists on a spectrum ranging from subtle structural narratives in mainstream journalism to overt ideological and extremist forms in far-right media, underlining its systemic nature across a diverse media landscape.

5.2.4 Effects of Anti-Migration Discourse on Migrants and Society

Media representations influence public opinion. Problem-orientation and dehumanisation of migration through negative framing, reproduction of stereotypes, and reduction to abstract categories in media are linked to growing hostility and support for restrictive policies. Negative media coverage can have social consequences such as discrimination and exclusion from locals, leading to stigmatisation, social isolation, and marginalisation of migrants. It can affect their sense of belonging and integration processes (Pearson et al., 2025). Thus, hostile media representation of migration can create hostile social environments between locals and migrants.

Another key issue is the lack of migrant voices in the media, especially as experts and individuals with agency. Migrants being spoken about rather than included in the exchange creates a one-sided discourse and reinforces unequal power structures. While participatory media projects can challenge dominant migration narratives, their reach is often limited (Pearson et al., 2025).

5.2.5 Broader implications

Traditional media is not a neutral reporter of migration debates but actively creates and shapes the perception of migration as a social and political problem. Framing of migration as a threat or crisis, dehumanisation, and elite-driven sourcing that excludes migrant voices help construct such narratives. Anti-migration discourse is embedded in everyday journalistic practices and does not only

¹ Original: “Es findet ein Krieg gegen Deutsche statt [...]. Dieser Krieg findet statt von innen: durch Politiker – und von außen: durch kulturfremde Gruppenvergewaltiger, Messerstecher, Totschläger und Mörder. Deutsche werden gejagt, vergewaltigt, geschlagen, gemessert, vertrieben, ermordet – im eigenen Land.”

occur in extreme media. It operates on a spectrum from implicit bias in mainstream media (*Tagesschau*) to explicit ideology in far-right media (*Compact*), showing its systemic character. These findings underline the necessity of understanding media discourse as a key mechanism in forming public opinion and the social realities of migrants, reinforcing broader societal dynamics of exclusion and inequality.

5.3 Focus on Digital Platforms as Sites of Far-Right Acculturation

Contemporary social media environments have become primary arenas of political socialisation, particularly for younger audiences. Research consistently shows that social media has overtaken traditional news sources as the dominant channel through which young people encounter political information (Newman, 2023). This shift carries significant implications for the circulation of extreme discourse. Platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube expand the reach of far-right messaging, whilst actively shaping the conditions under which it is encountered, processed, and normalised.

The democratising potential of online media is well documented. By lowering barriers to publication and distribution, digital platforms have enabled individuals and communities to share information, organise politically, and challenge narratives outside the constraints of legacy media and its attendant institutional and financial biases. In this sense, the structural openness of online environments represents a genuine expansion of communicative possibilities. This report does not discount those affordances. However, the same structural features that enable democratic participation, low barriers to entry, pseudonymity, algorithmic amplification of engagement, and the absence of editorial gatekeeping also create conditions uniquely conducive to the dissemination of harmful material. It is this dimension that the present report addresses, with a particular focus on the online communication of the far right. The analysis that follows draws on existing scholarship in digital media studies, extremism research, and platform studies, and is further informed by two recent empirical content analyses of far-right rhetorical strategies on Instagram, conducted by Benjamin Nangle and Leen d'Haenens as part of the DEMINE project. These studies provide original qualitative and multimodal evidence that grounds and extends the broader theoretical claims made throughout.

This represents a structural departure from traditional media environments. In broadcast and print media, editorial gatekeeping, however imperfect, imposed at least partial constraints on the visibility and reach of extreme content. Online platforms replace this architecture with engagement-maximising recommendation systems that are structurally indifferent to the valence or extremity of the content they surface, privileging instead the intensity of audience reaction. The result is a dissemination infrastructure qualitatively different in kind, not merely in scale, from anything available to far-right communicators in the pre-digital era.

A growing body of scholarship situates the far right not as a fixed ideological category but as a heterogeneous discursive and aesthetic space, identifiable through recurring thematic, stylistic, and affective repertoires rather than formal organisational affiliation (Pirro, 2023). Within networked digital environments, far-right publics function as affective communities, formations bound together through humour, resonance, and peer recognition that often take root in contexts marked by social alienation and weakened community infrastructures (Humphrey & Bliuc, 2022; Wilson, 2018). This underscores the importance of examining not only the emotional and infrastructural dynamics that sustain the appeal and circulation of online extreme discourse, alongside its ideological content.

5.3.1 Memetic Communication and Multimodal Mainstreaming

A distinctive feature of online extreme discourse, with no equivalent in traditional media environments, is the central role of meme culture. Internet memes, defined as digital items sharing common content, form, or stance, created with mutual awareness and transformed through circulation (Shifman, 2013), function as highly efficient vehicles for ideological messaging. Their concise, participatory, and cognitively accessible character makes them especially well-suited to environments of information overload and accelerated media consumption (Eriksen, 2016). Particularly high-profile foundational examples include “Pepe the frog”, an anthropomorphic cartoon frog character which became famously associated with alt-right groups and even violent extremists (Know Your Meme, n.d.). On short-form video platforms such as Instagram Reels and TikTok, memes operate as template-based performances built from recurring combinations of gesture, soundtrack, editing convention, and caption, with imitation and reenactment structurally encoded into the platform infrastructure itself (Grzenkiewicz & Wildfeuer, 2025; Han, 2024).

Far-right communicators exploit these dynamics through what Woods and Hahner (2020) term memetic *détournement*, the appropriation and repurposing of mainstream pop-cultural symbols to embed engaging ideological subtexts. Rather than stating extremist positions explicitly, much of this content uses ironic playfulness to broaden the boundaries of public acceptability, gradually shifting what counts as acceptable discourse (McSwiney & Sengul, 2024). This mechanism has no clear analogue in traditional media. The participatory, low-barrier infrastructure of social platforms enables ideological content to travel through the same channels as entertainment, making the distinction between the two increasingly difficult for audiences to identify and resist. Meme production thus fosters in-group identification while lowering the threshold of entry into radical milieus, functioning as a mechanism of acculturation and normalisation (Keenan, 2020).

Online extreme discourse is further distinguished by its multimodal character. Following Kress's (2010) social semiotic framework, meaning in digital media emerges not from individual elements in isolation but from the orchestrated combination of image, text, sound, and embodied performance. Research on short-form video specifically demonstrates how rhythmic editing, sonic cues, and affective visual design work together to produce immersive ideological experiences that bypass conscious critical processing (Han, 2024; Schmid, Schulze, & Drexel, 2024). This represents a qualitative departure from the predominantly text- or speech-based forms of extreme discourse that characterise much of traditional media, and significantly raises the difficulty of both audience resistance and platform moderation.

5.3.2 Affective Strategies and the Role of Positive Emotion

Traditional accounts of extreme discourse emphasise its reliance on fear, resentment, and outrage. Online environments, however, have enabled the development of a richer and more varied affective repertoire, in which positively valenced emotions, humour, nostalgia, pride, wholesomeness, and aspirational affect play a central role in softening, normalising, and mobilising extremist worldviews.

Roth et al.'s (2024) conceptual model of mainstreaming as a dual process is instructive here. They distinguish between content positioning, the insertion of radical ideas into wider discourse, and susceptibility, the emotional and dispositional attunement of audiences to those ideas. Online platforms are uniquely conducive to both dimensions simultaneously, enabling extreme content to be

aesthetically adapted to the emotional registers and participation norms of mainstream digital culture in ways that traditional broadcast environments structurally precluded.

Research across multiple platform contexts has documented the specific mechanisms through which this operates. Far-right content deploying positive emotions generates significantly higher engagement than content relying on fear or hatred alone (Berntzen, 2020). Humour in particular performs a dual function: it renders exclusionary messaging entertaining and shareable while providing plausible deniability, allowing creators and audiences alike to disavow serious intent while simultaneously circulating ideological content (Nagle, 2017). Schmid et al. (2024) confirm that the combination of humour and extreme rhetoric substantially increases viral reach, directly aiding the mainstreaming of far-right ideas. This dynamic has no equivalent in traditional media, where the formal register of broadcast content and the accountability structures of professional production constrained the extent to which ideological messaging could be embedded within entertainment.

Beyond humour, online extreme discourse increasingly deploys what can be termed soft affective aesthetics. Studies of "folkish Instagram" show how exclusionary narratives are refracted through aestheticised lifestyle imagery and euphemistic language, recasting white-identitarian content as self-improvement and cultural pride (Tebaldi & Plum, 2024). Maternal and traditional-gender lifestyle content normalises nativist worldviews for audiences, particularly women and younger users, who may not engage with overtly political material (Leidig, 2023; Argentino, 2021). Nostalgic imagery, alpine landscapes, mid-century family scenes, and romanticised rural aesthetics embed exclusionary ethnonationalist imaginaries within reassuring, sentimental forms, naturalising racial hierarchies through visual softness rather than explicit argumentation (Hakoköngäs et al., 2020).

At the more mobilising end of the spectrum, inspirational and aspirational aestheticisation frames ideological commitment as heroic awakening, civilisational duty, and collective purpose, drawing on imagery of martial valour, classical beauty ideals, and imperial grandeur to produce an embodied, aspirational identification with extremist imaginaries (Frischlich, 2021; Albertazzi & Bonansinga, 2024).

A further understanding of the deliberate and transmissible character of these mainstreaming strategies receives empirical grounding in a complementary DEMINE study examining 40 German-language YouTube vodcasts published between December 2024 and August 2025, comprising over 50 hours of content from AfD politicians, Identitarian activists, and alternative media figures (r (Arena & Oppenhaffen, 2026, referred to in adjacent report: Arena, Nangle, Azadi & d'Haenens, 2026).

The analysis identifies three integrated mechanisms through which extreme content circulates in long-form video without triggering moderation thresholds. Institutional delegitimation systematically portrays media, academia, courts, and civil society as captured by hostile elite interests, constructing an alternative epistemic landscape in which far-right actors present themselves as the sole credible sources. Statistical weaponisation deploys selective demographic data, crime statistics, and pseudo-scientific projections to normalise extreme narratives as empirical common sense. Deniability engineering substitutes euphemistic language, cultural framing, and centrist self-positioning for explicitly prosecutable expression, rendering individual statements formally defensible while their cumulative effect reconstructs extremist logic.

Crucially, 90 percent of the sampled videos include explicit meta-commentary on these strategies, speakers discuss Overton window shifts, coach peers on effective formulations, and track progress in

what can now be said publicly, confirming that mainstreaming operates as a deliberate and transmissible technique rather than incidental rhetorical drift.

The study further highlights the significance of content format as an independent variable: the extended runtime of long-form video provides the conversational space for all three mechanisms to unfold within a single piece of content, a condition the short-form environment structurally forecloses. This finding complements the report's broader argument that online extreme discourse cannot be adequately understood through fragment-level analysis of individual statements, but requires attention to cumulative effect across content.

5.3.3 Algorithmic Architecture and the Ecology of Amplification

Perhaps the most structurally consequential difference between traditional and online extreme discourse lies in the role of algorithmic recommendation systems. Unlike traditional broadcast media, where editorial gatekeeping, however imperfect, shapes what content reaches audiences, online platforms distribute content through opaque, engagement-maximising algorithms that systematically prioritise emotive material (Lim, 2020). This creates a structural alignment between the affective strategies employed by far-right communicators and the incentive logics of the platforms on which they operate.

The consequences of this alignment are significant. As engagement with far-right content increases, recommendation systems surface progressively more ideologically aligned material, generating recursive feedback loops that intensify both the volume and extremity of content encountered. Research on TikTok demonstrates that the platform's fast-paced, memetic interface reduces cognitive resistance and heightens emotional immediacy, enabling far-right content to spread with minimal friction (Ozduzen, Ferenczi, & Holmes, 2023). Crucially, algorithmic amplification extends beyond explicitly extremist accounts: content from creators entirely unaffiliated with the far right, including members of minority or marginalised communities, can be drawn into far-right viewing circuits when far-right users engage with it through outrage and ridicule, with recommendation systems responding to the intensity of the reaction regardless of its valence.

This dynamic produces what can be conceptualised as an affective–discursive ecology (Nangle & d'Haenens, in press): a curated environment in which ideology, emotion, and platform logics intersect and mutually reinforce one another. Within such ecologies, meaning is produced less through explicit political argumentation than through affective resonance, stylistic proximity, and repeated exposure. Ostensibly non-political or even progressive content becomes politicised through contextual adjacency, as benign material is algorithmically folded into circuits of far-right meaning. The result is a media environment in which extremist narratives become ambiently familiar, encountered not as overt ideology but as a diffuse aesthetic and emotional backdrop to everyday digital life.

A further structural feature of online extreme discourse with no traditional parallel is the cross-platform funnel: the deliberate use of mainstream platforms as entry points that redirect audiences toward spaces with weaker moderation and more explicitly ideological content. Research on far-right short-form video on Instagram documents how Reels are routinely embedded with hyperlinks to YouTube playlists, labelled, for instance, "Save Europe" or "Aryan Classics", where comment sections are less stringently moderated, and ideological expression becomes considerably more overt (Nangle & d'Haenens, in press). Shared audio tracks function as connective tissue across this ecology, linking mainstream-facing content to off-platform communities where acculturation is reinforced. This

pipeline represents a qualitatively different mode of radicalisation-adjacent exposure from anything available in traditional media environments, where the infrastructural separation between broadcast channels precluded comparable forms of deliberate audience migration.

The architecture of anonymity and pseudonymity, as well as factors like the online disinhibition effect (see Suler, 2004), further distinguishes online extreme discourse from its traditional counterparts. The removal of social accountability lowers barriers to participation and enables largely unchecked circulation of content, frequently amplified by automated networks and bots (Uyheng et al., 2022). The structural opacity of recommendation systems also means that the dynamics of radicalisation-adjacent exposure remain difficult to study, contest, or regulate, a challenge with no clear analogue in traditional media governance frameworks. A rare moment of infrastructural visibility emerged when X briefly introduced an "About This Account" feature surfacing users' likely base countries through platform metadata, exposing numerous high-follower nationalist accounts as operated from locations entirely inconsistent with the domestic identities they performed (Nangle & d'Haenens, in press). The episode illustrates how routine platform opacity actively enables the geographic inauthenticity that underpins much far-right translocal messaging.

5.3.4 Inauthentic Localisation, Sockpuppetry, and Serial Misattribution

A distinctive and undertheorised feature of online extreme discourse is the systematic fabrication of local authenticity through pseudonymous account practices and the deliberate misattribution of visual material. Both practices exploit platform affordances, low-barrier account creation, anonymity, the visual decontextualisation enabled by short-form video, in ways that have no equivalent in traditional media environments, where the production infrastructure of broadcast and print imposed at least partial accountability on content origin.

Far-right digital communication frequently deploys what are termed "sockpuppet" accounts: pseudonymous identities that simulate local citizenship in specific national contexts while being operated from elsewhere (Paterson, 2024). These accounts allow external actors to intervene in domestic political discourse by manufacturing the appearance of grassroots engagement, embedding coordinated ideological content within ostensibly organic public opinion (Chan, 2024; Kovic et al., 2018). Empirical indicators of such inauthenticity include inconsistencies in self-description, the use of American English idioms and spelling by accounts claiming European locations, and posting-time regularities misaligned with claimed time zones, detection heuristics that emerge from close reading of account behaviour rather than from platform metadata, which typically remains inaccessible to researchers (Nangle & d'Haenens, in press). Platform opacity means that observable instances of sockpuppetry almost certainly underrepresent actual prevalence. This practice aligns with documented influence operations by both state and non-state actors: analysis of social media traffic found that ostensibly Irish nationalist slogans were more frequently posted from accounts based in the US and UK than by Irish users, while the Russian Internet Research Agency's operations demonstrate how faux-local accounts can circulate divisive political messaging at scale by simulating grassroots engagement (Howard et al., 2018; Gallagher, 2023).

Distinct from simple misrepresentation of origin is the practice of serial misattribution: the systematic recycling of the same footage, recaptioned to claim multiple national locations simultaneously. Research on far-right Instagram content documents how a single decontextualised clip of a racial attack on public transport was recirculated across separate reels claiming the incident had occurred in Scotland, Italy, and Spain (Nangle & d'Haenens, in press). This practice is analytically separable from

straightforward misattribution: it is a scalable, low-effort technique for manufacturing transnational grievance resonance, allowing a single piece of content to generate outrage appeal across distinct national audiences through a shared civilisational narrative frame. The mechanism depends on platform affordances, the ease of reuploading and recaptioning short-form video, combined with the absence of systematic provenance verification, that have no equivalent in traditional broadcast environments, where footage origin was at least partially traceable through production infrastructure.

Importantly, not all producers of far-right-aligned content operate from ideological conviction. Research documents a growing category of financially motivated actors, unaffiliated with any movement, who produce and circulate extreme content for engagement-driven platform revenue (The Bureau of Investigative Journalism, 2025; Nangle & d'Haenens, in press). This monetisation-driven production is a structural consequence of platform incentive architectures that reward virality regardless of content valence, and it substantially complicates the assumption that inauthentic accounts are necessarily the product of coordinated political campaigns. It represents a category of far-right content production specific to online environments, with no meaningful analogue in traditional media.

5.3.5 Comment Sections as Acculturative Infrastructure

A further dimension of online extreme discourse that has no equivalent in traditional media is the role of participatory comment cultures as a secondary layer of ideological meaning-making. Traditional broadcast media were architecturally one-directional: audiences received content but lacked infrastructure for synchronous, public, and scalable collective response. Online platforms invert this structure, creating participatory spaces in which audience engagement is simultaneously a measure of algorithmic visibility, a mechanism of community formation, and, in the case of far-right content, a site of ideological clarification and escalation.

Research on far-right short-form video documents how comment sections function as acculturative spaces that frequently operate at a more explicit ideological register than the primary content to which they respond (Nangle & d'Haenens, in press). Primary content is often constructed to maintain plausible deniability through irony, ambiguity, or aesthetic detachment; comment sections, subject to comparatively permissive moderation, surface the ideological intent that the content itself obscures. This is facilitated through emoji-coded dog whistles (with similar rhetorical techniques sometimes referred to as “algo speak”) specifically designed to evade automated content moderation: the use of a juice box emoji to signify “Jews,” a crescent moon followed by “ancer” to equate Islam with disease, and double lightning bolt emojis to reference the Nazi SS insignia are documented examples of how platform affordances are systematically exploited to enable extremist signalling beneath the threshold of automated detection. Similarly, GIF-based commentary, such as the circulation of a Roman legionary salute from the HBO series Rome as a visual stand-in for the Nazi salute, allows users to convey extremist alignment through historical analogy while maintaining deniability.

These participatory dynamics are further intensified by what research identifies as a dogpiling effect: coordinated or semi-coordinated swarming of posts by aligned accounts that overwhelms dissenting voices, generates the impression of mass consensus, and reinforces the perceived legitimacy and inevitability of far-right positions (Nangle & d'Haenens, in press). Algorithmic comment ranking may amplify this dynamic further by foregrounding comments that align with a user's inferred ideological preferences, selectively suppressing dissent, and deepening the perception of consensus. The cumulative effect is a participatory infrastructure that does not merely reflect existing extremist

sentiment but actively produces and normalises it, a structural feature of online discourse with no equivalent in the audience reception dynamics of traditional media.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

This report has mapped the structural and communicative differences between traditional and online extreme discourse, with particular attention to how digital environments reshape the conditions under which such discourse is produced, circulated, and normalised. The findings point consistently in one direction: online platforms do not simply extend pre-existing forms of extreme communication but qualitatively transform them, introducing dynamics of amplification, affective embedding, inauthentic coordination, and participatory escalation that have no meaningful equivalent in traditional media environments.

The core discursive repertoires of extreme discourse — dehumanisation, othering, threat construction, moralised language — remain largely consistent across traditional and online media. What changes is the infrastructure through which they operate. Traditional media constrain and contextualise extreme content through institutional gatekeeping and professional norms, even as they reproduce structural biases through elite sourcing, crisis framing, and the systematic exclusion of migrant voices. Online platforms invert this logic, replacing gatekeeping with engagement-maximising algorithms structurally indifferent to the extremity of the content they surface.

The affective dimension of online extreme discourse represents a qualitative shift that existing analytical frameworks have been slow to capture. Far-right communicators have developed a varied affective repertoire extending well beyond fear and outrage to encompass humour, nostalgia, aspirational aesthetics, and soft lifestyle content, enabling ideological messaging to circulate through mainstream entertainment channels and normalise among audiences who would not engage with overtly political material. Practices specific to online environments — sockpuppetry, serial misattribution, cross-platform funnelling, emoji-coded dog whistles, and monetisation-driven content production — further complicate both the study and governance of extreme discourse. The role of platforms as infrastructural actors remains the most significant under-theorised gap in the existing literature.

6.2 Recommendations

The findings carry implications across research, platform governance, media literacy and policy.

For research, the field requires analytical frameworks that move beyond text-centred approaches to account for the multimodal, affective, and infrastructural dimensions of online extreme discourse. Platforms themselves should be treated as primary objects of analysis. Investment in cross-platform tracking, multimodal content analysis, and the study of coordinated inauthentic behaviour will be essential for keeping pace with rapidly evolving communicative practices.

For platform governance, the structural alignment between algorithmic recommendation logics and far-right affective strategies demands regulatory attention beyond individual content moderation. Engagement-maximising architectures that systematically amplify emotive material represent an infrastructural problem that takedown decisions cannot address. Transparency requirements for recommendation systems, provenance verification for short-form video, and accountability for

monetisation practices that reward virality over accuracy are among the structural interventions the evidence supports.

For media literacy and intervention, effective responses must address the specific strategies through which online extreme discourse operates: the irony and plausible deniability of memetic content, affective softening through lifestyle aesthetics, and the cross-platform funnel as a deliberate radicalisation-adjacent pathway. Generic digital literacy programmes are insufficient; interventions must be platform-specific, age-appropriate, and empirically grounded. The DEMINE project is developing complementary responses to this challenge. Platform-level psychological inoculation interventions that pre-emptively equip users with the cognitive tools to identify and resist the rhetorical and affective strategies through which extreme discourse operates, addressing the mechanisms of persuasion rather than individual pieces of content. Additionally, HateLess: Together Against Hatred, a scientifically validated, school-based prevention programme for adolescents aged 12 to 16, which aims to transform young people from passive observers into active upstanders against hate speech, improving both online and offline social environments. Together, these interventions reflect a considered division of labour: platform-level inoculation targets the moment of exposure, while school-based prevention builds durable protective capacities in the cohort most heavily socialised through algorithmic media.

For policymakers, the evidence supports treating the infrastructure of online extreme discourse as a matter of public concern. Regulatory frameworks such as the EU's Digital Services Act provide relevant instruments, but their implementation must attend to the specific mechanisms identified here: algorithmic amplification, inauthentic coordination, cross-platform funnelling and the monetisation incentives sustaining engagement-driven production of harmful content. The scalability of effective interventions depends on institutional support, curricular integration, and coordination between educational authorities, civil society and platform providers. Further policy recommendations will be made as the DEMINE project develops and DCs work with non-academic secondments.

The challenge posed by online extreme discourse is infrastructural as much as it is communicative. Effective responses require structural interventions in platform design, regulatory architecture and educational provision — not extensions of approaches developed for a media environment that no longer exists.

7. References

- Agarwal, L., Priti, Jaiswal, S., & Kumar, S. (2023). Media ownership and its influence on political reporting. *Journal of Nonlinear Analysis and Optimization*, 13(01), 78–86. <https://doi.org/10.36893/jnao.2022.v13i02.078-086>
- Arzheimer, K. (2015). The AfD: finally a successful Right-Wing populist eurosceptic party for Germany? *West European Politics*, 38(3), 535–556. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2015.1004230>
- Arena, C.C., Nangle, B., Azadi, T. & d’Haenens, L. (2026). *Conceptual Framework for Understanding Commonalities and Differences in Extreme Political Content Using Misinformation on Different Social Media Platforms*. KU Leuven, Leuven: DEMINE.
- Avaaz. (2019, May 22). Far-right networks of deception: Avaaz investigation uncovers flood of disinformation, triggering shutdown of Facebook pages with over 500 million views ahead of EU elections. <https://avaaz.org>
- Berry, M., Garcia-Blanco, I., & Moore, K. (2016). Press Coverage of the Refugee and Migrant Crisis in the EU: A Content Analysis of Five European Countries. *United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)*. <https://www.unhcr.org/media/press-coverage-refugee-and-migrant-crisis-eu-content-analysis-five-european-countries>
- Chadwick, A. (2017). *The Hybrid Media System: Politics and Power* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Chan, J. (2024). Online Astroturfing: A Problem Beyond Disinformation. *Philosophy & Social Criticism*, 50(3), 507–528. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01914537221108467>
- da Rosa Lazarotto, B. (2023). The Grass is Not Always Greener on the Other Side: The Use of Digital Astroturfing to Spread Disinformation and the Erosion of the Rule of Law. *LSU Journal for Social Justice & Policy*, 3, 113–124. <https://digitalcommons.law.lsu.edu/jsjp/vol3/iss1/9/>
- Eberl, J.-M., Meltzer, C. E., Heidenreich, T., Herrero, B., Theorin, N., Lind, F., Berganza, R., Boomgaarden, H. G., Schemer, C., & Strömbäck, J. (2018). The European media discourse on immigration and its effects: A literature review. *Annals of the International Communication Association*, 42(3), 207–223. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1234055/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Fuller, J. M. (2024). Media discourses of migration: A focus on Europe. *Sociology Compass*, 18(2). <https://compass.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/lnc3.12526>
- Gallagher, C. (2023, December 5). Most 'Ireland is full' and 'Irish lives matter' Online Posts Originate Abroad. *The Irish Times*. <https://www.irishtimes.com/crime-law/2023/12/05/most-ireland-is-full-and-irish-lives-matter-online-posts-originate-abroad/>
- Glicker, M., & Watts, C. (2021, February 25). 24 Group: How obscure news sites selectively spread pro-Kremlin disinformation. Alliance for Securing Democracy at the German Marshall Fund of the United States. <https://securingdemocracy.gmfus.org/24-group-how-obscure-news-sites-selectively-spread-pro-kremlin-disinformation/>
- Howard, P. N., Ganesh, B., Liotsiou, D., Kelly, J., & François, C. (2018). *The IRA, social media and political polarization in the United States, 2012–2018*. Project on Computational Propaganda, Oxford

- Internet Institute. <https://comprop.oii.ox.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/sites/93/2018/12/The-IRA-Social-Media-and-Political-Polarization.pdf>
- Hutter, S., & Kriesi, H. (2019). Politicizing Europe in times of crisis. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26(7), 996–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2019.1619801>
- Know Your Meme. (n.d.). *Pepe the Frog*. Retrieved April 29, 2026, from <https://knowyourmeme.com/memes/pepe-the-frog>
- Kovic, M., Rauchfleisch, A., Sele, M., & Caspar, C. (2018). Digital Astroturfing in Politics: Definition, Typology, and Countermeasures. *Studies in Communication Sciences*, 18(1), 69–85. <https://doi.org/10.24434/j.scoms.2018.01.005>
- Krzyżanowski, M., Triandafyllidou, A., & Wodak, R. (2018). The mediatization and the politicization of the “refugee crisis” in Europe. *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 16(1–2), 1–14. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15562948.2017.1353189#d1e201>
- Martin, G. J., & McCrain, J. (2019). Local news and national politics. *American Political Science Review*, 113(2), 372–384. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-political-science-review/article/local-news-and-national-politics/C8EEA488A777C37C7987964F8F85AEB5>
- Maurer, M., Jost, P., Kruschinski, S., & Haßler, J. (2021). *Fünf Jahre Medienberichterstattung über Flucht und Migration*. Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz. https://www.stiftung-mercator.de/content/uploads/2021/07/Medienanalyse_Flucht_Migration.pdf
- McCombs, M. E., & Shaw, D. L. (1972). The agenda-setting function of mass media. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 36(2), 176–187.
- Middle East Monitor. (2024, July 17). Israeli ministry funding multi-million-dollar disinformation campaign spreading Islamophobia. <https://www.middleeastmonitor.com/20240717-israeli-ministry-funding-multi-million-dollar-disinformation-campaign-spreading-islamophobia/>
- Nangle, B., & Blažyte, G. (2026). The construction of hostility towards migrants. In *Mobility & politics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-05958-1>
- Nangle, B. M., & d’Haenens, L. (2026). Affective–discursive ecologies of the far right: Multimodal softening, mobilisation and algorithmic proximity on Instagram. *New Media & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448261428632>
- Nangle, B., & d’Haenens, L. (under review). Projecting the Meta-Community: Translocalized and Transhistoricized Narratives in Far-Right Short-Form Video Culture. *Journal of Right-Wing Studies*.
- ndr.de. (2024, January 2). *20 Uhr-Ausgabe bleibt Deutschlands meist gesehene Nachrichtensendung und punktet auch bei den Jüngeren*. https://www.ndr.de/der_ndr/presse/mitteilungen/20-Uhr-Ausgabe-bleibt-Deutschlands-meist-gesehene-Nachrichtensendung-und-punktet-auch-bei-den-Juengeren,pressemeldungndr24366.html
- O’Keeffe, C. (2024, May 6). Foreign actors are influencing more extreme protests on domestic scene. Irish Examiner. <https://www.irishexaminer.com/news/spotlight/arid-41387437.html>

- Paterson, G. (2024). Sock Puppetry in Online Communication. *Philosophy*, 99(3), 461–478. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0031819124000123>
- Pearson, B., Ryan, S., & Antoniak, M. (2025). Integration and the Media: reflections from a participatory project in Glasgow. In *A Handbook of Integration with Refugees Global Learnings from Scotland* (pp. 201–215). Channel View Publications.
- Reichwingwatch. (2025, November 23). [Instagram post documenting foreign-run MAGA and “America First” sock-puppet accounts exposed following X’s “About This Account” feature rollout] [Instagram post]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/DRaLHo5kXfH/>
- Robins-Early, N. (2022, February 21). Disinformation for profit: Scammers cash in on conspiracy theories. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/media/2022/feb/20/facebook-disinformation-ottawa-social-media>
- Shoemaker, P. J., & Vos, T. P. (2009). *Gatekeeping Theory*. Routledge.
- Shoemaker, P. J., & Reese, S. D. (2014). *Mediating the Message in the 21st Century: A Media Sociology Perspective* (3rd ed.). Routledge. https://psipp.itb-ad.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Pamela-J.-Shoemaker-Stephen-D.-Reese-Mediating-the-Message-in-the-21st-Century_-A-Media-Sociology-Perspective-2013-Routledge.pdf
- Suler, J. (2004). The online disinhibition effect. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 7(3), 321–326. <https://doi.org/10.1089/1094931041291295>
- Taouk, M., Workman, M., & Hair, J. (2025, December 16). Racist and antisemitic false information spreads online following Bondi Beach terrorism attack. *ABC News*. <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2025-12-17/abc-news-verify-misinformation-bondi-terrorist-attack/106150286>
- The Bureau of Investigative Journalism. (2025, November 16). King of slop: How anti-migrant AI content made one Sri Lankan influencer rich. <https://www.thebureauinvestigates.com/stories/2025-11-16/king-of-slop-how-anti-migrant-ai-content-made-one-sri-lankan-influencer-rich>
- University of Oxford. (2021, January 13). Social media manipulation by political actors an industrial scale problem – Oxford report. <https://www.ox.ac.uk/news/2021-01-13-social-media-manipulation-political-actors-industrial-scale-problem-oxford-report>
- Verfassungsschutz Brandenburg. (2022). *Verfassungsschutzbericht Brandenburg 2022*. https://mik.brandenburg.de/sixcms/media.php/9/VS_Bericht_2022_Pressefassung_neu.pdf
- White, D. M. (1950). The “gatekeeper”: A case study in the selection of news. *Journalism Quarterly*, 27(4), 383–390.